

FOREIGN COUNTRIES' EXPERIENCE IN REGULATING THE SILENT ECONOMY

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Abstract. The main driving forces behind the size and growth of the shadow economy appear to be the increasing burden of taxation and social payments, combined with broader state regulation. Weak and arbitrary enforcement of laws and regulations encourages shadow economic activity; the findings highlight the importance of the rule of law in curbing corruption and related shadow economic activity.

This study examines the experience of foreign countries in regulating the Shadow Economy, as well as the work of similar experiments.

Keywords. Economy, tax, activity, labor, income, regime, state, order.

Аннотация. Основными движущими силами размеров и роста теневой экономики, по-видимому, являются растущее бремя налогообложения и социальных льгот в сочетании с более широкой деятельностью государственного регулирования. Слабое и произвольное применение законов и нормативных актов поощряет подпольную экономическую деятельность; Результаты исследования подчеркивают важность верховенства закона в борьбе с коррупцией и связанной с ней теневой экономической деятельностью.

В данном исследовании проведено научное исследование опыта зарубежных стран по регулированию теневой экономики, а также деятельности подобных экспериментов.

Ключевые слова. Экономика, налог, деятельность, труд, доход, режим, государство, порядок.

Introduction. Taxes and social security contributions are added to the cost of labor in the formal economy, and this in turn is one of the main factors that ensure the growth of the informal economy. If the gap between the total cost of labor in the formal economy and the income that reaches workers after taxes is large, this encourages employers and employees to move into the informal economy to reduce this gap. Since the gap depends in particular on the social security system and the tax regime, these are considered to be the main factors that cause the development of the informal economy. For example, in Germany and Austria, the tax and social security contributions paid by firms and their

employees make a large difference in the effective wage for workers. This difference is more likely to encourage workers to move into the informal economy than to continue working in the formal sector.

Several studies have found strong evidence that the tax regime has an impact on the informal economy. In Austria, the direct tax burden, including social security contributions, has the largest impact on the growth of the informal economy. The burden of the tax system and the social security contributions attached to it, as well as the number of regulations affecting firms and workers and the complexity of the system, have a significant impact on this process. Similar results have been observed for the Scandinavian countries, Germany and the United States. In these countries, the increased tax burden and the complexity of the tax system create a strong incentive for the growth of the informal economy, as employers and employees are more likely to seek to avoid the formal system. Participation in the shadow economy not only allows for tax reductions but also, in some cases, the ability to bypass bureaucratic processes. In the United States, analysis shows that as the marginal federal personal income tax rate increases by one percentage point, other things being equal, the shadow economy grows by 1.4 percentage points.

Similarly, maintaining the highest marginal income tax rate in the United States may hinder further growth of the informal economy.

Results and discussion. A study of Quebec City, Canada, shows that people are highly mobile between the formal and informal economies, and as net wages in the formal economy increase, they work less in the informal economy. This study also suggests that where people perceive the tax rate to be too high, an increase in the (marginal) tax rate leads to a reduction in tax revenues.

Government regulations can significantly increase the cost of labor for firms in the formal economy. Such regulations include licensing requirements, labor market regulations, trade barriers, and labor restrictions for foreigners. These regulatory constraints lead to additional costs and red tape in the formal economy, which creates strong incentives for firms to shift to the informal economy in order to reduce their costs and operate more efficiently.

Employers in the formal economy, in order to reduce the additional costs that are passed on to their employees, often encourage them to work outside the formal system, often in the informal economy. This, in turn, slows down the growth of the formal economy and increases the share of the informal economy. Such growth of the informal economy, in turn, leads to a decrease in government revenues, tax evasion and a deterioration in the quality of public services. A

number of studies show that countries with more regulated economies have larger informal economies. For example, among 84 developing, transition and advanced economies, a one-point increase in the regulation index (from 1 to 5) is associated with a 10 percent increase in the informal economy.

In particular, labor market regulation has a significant impact on employers' costs and workers' incentives. In many OECD countries, high total labor costs are an important reason for high rates of formal unemployment and, at the same time, the expansion of the informal economy, which provides employment for many officially unemployed people. Some governments (e.g., France) and unions (e.g., Germany) have limited the hours that people can work in the formal economy in an attempt to reduce unemployment. The aim is to redistribute the limited amount of work in a fairer way, but forced reductions in formal jobs can also push people into the informal economy. For example, after Volkswagen in Germany reduced working hours, there was a significant increase in the number of homes renovated and renovated in areas where employees live compared to other areas.

Countries with strong, effective government institutions tend to have smaller underground economies. Research shows that higher taxes alone do not cause the underground economy to grow. Instead, the tax system and the government's inefficient and arbitrary application of rules contribute to the expansion of the underground economy. Therefore, if the tax system is fair and transparent, the underground economy can be reduced. A tightly regulated economy, combined with a weak and arbitrary rule of law, creates a fertile ground for underground activity. This is also the environment in which corruption flourishes.

Few studies have empirically examined the relationship between corruption and the shadow economy, but they do show that countries with higher levels of corruption tend to have larger shadow economies. Corruption is essentially the abuse of public power for private gain.

Activities that create opportunities for corruption include:

- regulating or licensing the practice of certain activities (such as opening a shop or driving a taxi);
- zoning land and other similar official decisions;
- managing or making available goods and services provided by the government;
- controlling decisions on the procurement of public investment contracts;
- controlling the granting of tax breaks; and

controlling public sector recruitment and promotion.

A number of studies have found a direct correlation between a country's reduction in corruption and the size of the shadow economy. All studies have shown that more corruption leads to a larger underground economy.

One of these studies notes that "some wealthy OECD countries, as well as some in Eastern Europe, have a good balance of relatively low tax and regulatory burdens, high revenue mobilization, good rule of law and corruption controls, and a (relatively) small informal economy." In contrast, a number of countries in Latin America have their own bad characteristics: high tax and regulatory burdens and firm burdens, weak rule of law, and relatively high levels of bribery and activity in the informal economy.

Conclusion. Changes in the size of the shadow economy can be reflected in the following changes:

Monetary indicators. Shadow economy transactions are usually carried out in cash. Increased activity in the shadow economy can increase the demand for currency.

Labor market participation and working hours. As the number of people working in the shadow sector increases, participation in the formal economy may decrease. Similarly, as people work more hours in the shadow sector, the hours worked in the formal economy may decrease.

Output statistics. As the shadow economy grows, productive resources, particularly labor, move at least partially outside the formal economy. This shift can reduce the formal growth rate of the economy.

Theoretical and empirical studies cannot fully explain how the growth of the shadow economy or the informal sector affects economic growth. Some argue that the shadow economy reduces GDP growth. They argue that a reduction in the shadow economy increases tax revenues, stimulates government spending, especially on infrastructure and services that support the expansion of production, and leads to an increase in overall economic growth.

Conversely, the informal sector is more competitive and efficient than the formal sector, so growth in the informal economy stimulates overall economic growth.

Analysts and policymakers should be aware that estimates of the informal economy can vary widely depending on the estimation method. There is no "best" estimation method; each approach has its strengths and weaknesses, and provides its own insights and results. Table 3.1 describes common methods. The currency demand and latent variable approaches are the most commonly used.

List of references used:

1. Abulqosimov H.P., Muminov N.G. Xufyona iqtisodiyot: o'quv qo'llanma. H.P. Abulqosimov, N.G. Muminov – T.: Yangi nashr, 2020. – B.304.;
2. “O'zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi to'g'risida” O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining farmoni, O'zbekiston Respublikasi qonun hujjatlari to'plami, 2017.;
3. Geoffrey L. The People's Budget: an Edwardian Tragedy// Georgist Journal. 2008. URL:<http://www.georgistjournal.org/2012/09/14/the-peoples-budget-an-edwardian-tragedy/> (дата обращения: 11.11.2018).;
4. WilliamManchester, TheLastLion Winston Spencer Churchill, Visions of Glory 1874-1932(1983), pp.408–409.;
5. BRING ON THE LIGHT: REDUCTION OF THE CORPORATE SHADOW ECONOMY BY TAX REFORM Vincentas Rolandas Giedraitis, Andriy Stavytsky, Ganna Kharlamova, Erstida Ulvidienė;

